

The Impact of Self-Marketing to Find a Job: The Case Study of Undergraduate Students in Northern Iraq

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Abstract:

This study aims to explore that undergraduate students in Northern Iraq have the ability to see the idea of self-marketing to find the job and they can be familiar with their branding. Semi-structured interviews collected the data and analyzed it using content analysis. The sampling strategy employed in this study is the maximum sampling of variations. The outcomes of this thesis reveal that the effectiveness and efficiency of self-marketing are the foremost way to undergraduate students (universities and institutes) in Northern Iraq to thrive the compete of finding a job. The undergraduate students need to understand from the self-marketing, particularly concentrate on the important parts such as (CV, interview, social media, skills, experience, and certifications) to a career fair. They should have the ability to focus on different ways to engage in a job. Through this method, the undergraduate students will be able to make important progress in finding a reasonable job.

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1- Introduction

Unemployment is today a world phenomenon that is increasing day after day and there are many reasons that have caused occur this situation, especially the technological advance, apolitical, and economic phenomenon that has an impact on the jobless. Above all, nowadays the Covid-nineteen is the main reason to make unemployment. This condition could make it difficult to find a position to succeed, so the undergraduate students must be prepared to take part in this competitor and pay attention to their abilities and willingness to do the best self-marketing to seek the work. Self-marketing is one of the first things that must be acknowledged is the virtue of humility. There is a fine line between good, healthy self-promotion and egotistical boasting (Beals, 2008). The key to self-marketing is to promote yourself while making it look as if you're not trying. Self-marketing is more art than science. There's a fine line between self-marketing and egotistical boasting. Develop self-marketing and expertise it's more much easier to help himself if jobseekers are an expert in something (Beals, 2008). Maybe to jobseeker's surprise, becoming an experience in something is not essentially difficult. Jobseeker's behavior and the image is an important part of self-marketing. (Beals, 2008). Obviously the usage and the implementation of information technology by firms is considered as a competitive advantage that can differentiate the firm from its competitors especially with the globalization that has affected all types of businesses and pushed them to compete globally and not locally. There are many ways in self-marketing that help the job seekers, especially undergraduate students to find the job, such as (SM, CV, interview, and skills). Nowadays there is a transition in digital marketing (DM) and that relies more on social media (SM), in particular, to promote and advertise a product or services (Sinha, 2007). Additionally, the implementation of new digital technologies has created various opportunities for job seekers (Garrison, 2001). The social media network offers the opportunity to create and maintain a personality quickly and more cost-effectively. However, the incentives provided by social media to build a successful self-marketing identity are not restricted to companies or organizations alone. On the opposite, it is now more than ever feasible for ordinary people to equally take advantage of all the resources provided by social networking (Meiselwitz, g. 2019). Reed (2018) explained that the curriculum vitae are a Latin expression and translate to one's course of life, more commonly known as a CV in the modern world. Over and above the tactic your curriculum vitae are written and arranged lie important aim: Your curriculum vitae will encourage trust and motivate a recruiter to undertake the leap of faith by giving you a new individual interview is often a challenge to an interviewer, implying the CV mistakes and apparent exaggerations are an immense turnoff. On the other hand, there are plenty of ways in which you can present yourself as the most credible job applicant (Reed, 2018), Except for this, in today's fiercely competitive job market, interviewing may seem like walking through a minefield. Recent developments in organizational planning and development have contributed to drastic shifts in what managers search for in potential hires, so during the interview, you will be questioned regarding the kinds of issues (Yeager & Hough, 2019).

Besides, Skills are the technical competences a person possesses. Skills are a fairly simple concept; soft abilities are much more difficult to pin down applying to as they do to a range of skills. Essential Skills: Each and every student must possess the essential skills in order to strive and to survive in the competitive world. The learners in the traditional setting predominantly constitute student preparing for a career. The learning system focuses on class-room based students and overarches the design and operation of the teaching (Bhatnagar & Srivastava, 2012), Recently in ERBIL, Northern Iraq-there's an issue with Iraq's

next administration. About half of the workforce is under 19 years of age, and unemployment for 15-24 year-olds is now 18 percent (Edwards & Rwanduzy, 2018). Their disillusionment will only grow unless opportunities are created for them. The unkempt according to recent figures from the United Nations Development Program (UNDP). One particular concern is unemployment among young people. Given the weak turnout at the May 12 parliamentary polls, the continued mass exodus to Europe, and the growing appeal of paramilitary groups providing alternative paying jobs, many are losing confidence in government efforts to fix the issue (Edwards & Rwanduzy, 2018). Many will be surprised to learn that the unemployment rate among young people with higher education is actually higher. This politically active community has high hopes and does not react well to frustration like those who started protesting in the Arab world in 2011 (Edwards & Rwanduzy, 2018).

2- Literature Review

2.1- Self-marketing

Self-marketing is one of the first things that must be acknowledged is the virtue of humility. There is a fine line between good, healthy self-promotion and egotistical boasting. The key to self-marketing is to promote yourself while making it look as if you're not trying. Self-marketing is more art than science (Silber, 2010). There's a fine line between self-marketing and egotistical boasting. Most of the networking challenge involves an element of self – marketing or self – promotion. Self-marketing is a process of preparing yourself in a favorable light and projecting an appropriate professional image through the things you say about yourself and through written materials. Self-marketing is necessary so that people will see you as deserving of the opportunities that you seek and so that they will be more inclined to share time and expertise with you. If you're not marketing yourself, you are going to fall behind someone else. You need to embrace and actively engage with the concept of self-promotion or else you'll always be on the fringe You need credentials and visibility (Silber, 2010). Self-marketing is one of the harshest things a creative person has to do. It is the most crucial one, too. What separates the successful creative person from the struggle artist flush with fame, fortune, and rewarding career? It's not talent or luck. It's the ability to promote yourself and the work that gives you the exposure you need to stand out from the crowd and make it (Silber, 2010).

2.2- Personal Branding

As explained by works (2019), personal branding is simply the unique way or method you promote yourself. It is how you want the world to envision your personality. Think of personal branding as telling your story in a way that reflects your values, skills, and personality. What is your brand? Whether you are known for your tweets or you are still using a typewriter, you have a brand that exists both on and off-line. The idea of personal branding sometimes makes people uneasy. The benefits of personal branding numbers aside, the most important to focus on personal branding is to help yourself (works, 2019). Most people fail to describe themselves appropriately so they lack the know-how of their self – projection. Creating a personal brand involves looking at yourself inwardly, reflecting on your attributes, and designing a template on how you want people to see you (works, 2019).

2.3- The Steps for Effective Self-Marketing

Know who you are: job seeker's interests, strength, values, personal qualities, and work style. Know what you want: the goals and purposes job seeker is trying to attain through networking. The first tool in self - marketing is the self – marketing sound bite:

- A self-marketing sound bite is a brief spoken or written statement that identifies who job

seekers are and what job seekers need.

- Job seeker self-marketing sound bite is the keystone of all job seekers networking communication (Tullier, 2004).

2.4- Creativity in Self Marketing

2.4.1 - Who-are-you?

Taking stock of who you are your good, strengths, values, personal qualities, and work style is a significant foundation for most networking communication. Knowing yourself ensures that job seekers be able to transmit to others what makes him unique job seekers. Networking for job seekers or career development, for example, requires that the job seeker sells other persons on job seeker's strengths and abilities (Tullier, 2014). Both job seeker's skills are the first step in having a convincing self-marketing. Networking to help job seeker make a career decision also requires that job seeker have a solid handle on which you are and what your imports are so that as you learn about various career possibilities, the job seeker can law out options that don't fit and the law in the ones that do (Tullier, 2014). Self –awareness also empowers job seekers to understand the way job seekers go about networking. It helpful job seeker to recognize his strengths and weaknesses and methods that fit the job seeker's personality style (Tullier, 2014).

2.4.2 - Know Yourself

Define yourself; don't worry about where in the future you want to be. Rather, look at who you are today, what you've already achieved, what you're doing right now (Brewer, 2018). Identifying and being aware of job seeker having knowledge, skills, experiences, and character traits are a necessary step to develop being able to market yourself successfully. In school, students have the opportunity to use teachers' feedback on the progress of their strengths and weaknesses in both technical and transferable skill areas (Brewer, 2018). Technical skills during your studies and will learn more while on the job. Transferable skills are those abilities and skills that could be easily transferred to a diversity of work settings (Todd, 2012).

2.4.3 - Organize Personal

There are a number of items you need to plan to create a productive career quest. It includes your schedule, your tools, your clothing, your traveling method, advertising your meals, and rest, one thing that will help you reduce stress is establishing your own workday schedule (Keith, 2019). Never forget that a job search is a job it is work. Like any other job. Setting your own workday routine is one aspect that can help you raise the tension. Never forget that searching for a job is a job it is a job. Like every other job. Prepare your clothes the night before or for the entire week. Being dressed for success and being organized will heighten your confidence, make you a litter more relaxed, and help eliminate some of the negative emotions (Keith, 2019). Look at each successful stage of the job search as an accomplishment that puts you one step closer to reaching your employment goals. For example, you get a job lead. That is an accomplishment. Next, an interview is set for you, again another successful step. Also, keep in mind that getting you closer to your job. Prepare your clothes for the whole week or the night before. Getting prepared and coordinated for performance would improve your trust, render you a litter more confident and help remove any of the negative emotions. (Keith, 2019).

2.5- Increasing Your Marketability

Concerning Keith (2019), These days, looking for a job means creating and executing a complete self - marketing campaign. The begging of marketing yourself is to know you. People have heard the expression of retail sales, "know your product" your product is you and you couldn't sell yourself until you know your strengths and weaknesses. Anybody you 're talking

to is a potential job as a leader. If you only respond to news, ads, and web ads, your chances are narrowing, if it is too thin, the majority of the job can be slipping right through your net. None of the positions were advertised (Keith, 2019; Prabhu et al. 2019). You need to get into the hidden job market. How? It is good to respond to the Internet and classified ads, but add other avenues for job searching. Set aside the time you need to contact companies that you think may have jobs that you can do (Keith, 2019). The idea of selling oneself or talking highly of one's achievement is alien to many doctors. However, there are huge variations in this even with the group doctor's and some cultures and personalities naturally emphasize their achievements and others are more reserved about them (Sara & Vincent, 2012).

2.6- Educational Qualifications and Personal Development

Qualifications and personal development are fully aware that colleges are beginning to share the same view too, as most of the student who graduates from college become qualified at an equal level (Brisk, 2011). Personal growth has now become a key feature of the CV as it displays that a person is continually looking to improve themselves wherever visible, whether this is polishing up on their skills, searching for opportunities to becoming most of the skills and gaining experience and knowledge and perhaps building on the interest which has an influence on other (Brisk, 2011).

2.7- Skills Development

Skills can take a lot of different forms. Let's start by thinking of some kinds of skills with which job seekers are previously familiar. Make an absolute list of what's requisite for the job: the qualities, skills, and characteristics necessary to accomplish the role to complete. Now, look at the job seeker's own experience and skills. Though everything that has helped progress suitable traits, including:

- Jobseeker current job;
- Jobseeker has had a job in the past; -
- Voluntary locations such as work knowledge, unpaid work, community work, and sports group;

Try to Check all job seeker's experience and qualify. Although skills acquired in the workplace are important, there is nothing to stop job seekers including anything that has helped job seekers improve the skills necessary (Gallagher, 2010).

Skills are the technical competences a person possesses. Skills are a fairly simple concept; soft abilities are much more difficult to pin down applying to as they do to a range of skills. Essential Skills: Each and every student must possess the essential skills in order to strive and to survive in the competitive world. The learners in the traditional setting predominantly constitute student preparing for a career. The learning system focuses on class-room based students and overarches the design and operation of the teaching (Bhatnagar & Srivastava, 2012). As well as, Study skills include all the abilities that allow the demands of academic and professional pursuits to be addressed (Nambirajan & Prabhu 2011; Reed, 2018). For people just starting a study course, these skills include being able to deal with all the intellectuals, Emotional and psychological problems that are a component of the day-to-day student demands. Beyond the coping skills are those that enable students to do their chosen disciplines truly well. Study skills that are mastered at university or are central to what everyone has to offer as a graduate and/or professional for some people earlier when studying at school(Reed, 2018). Some people would even suggest that a university degree's main contribution is to give a person the ability to study. It is these abilities that will help the person throughout the remainder of their career. The programmers for business and management are built to allow students to learn a broad range of skills including:

- An ability to perceive and benefit from the experience

- Effective communication skills
- Effective learning skills
- Effective self- management skills
- Information skills
- Leadership skills
- Problem solving skills

It is something that you are doing well. You have a lot of skills. You might work best with your hands, for example, or you could be really good at math's. Working in an occupation that uses your skills is much more pleasant (Reed, 2018).

2.8- Jobseeker's Ability

Specialized areas of experience tried a variety of opportunities for persons with kind abilities and skills, for example; A person who has the strongest mathematical skills may select to pursue a more quantitative path in his field than a person with strongest verbal skills and abilities would. It is significant to make a truthful assessment of (Solomon et al. 2012). Jobseeker skills and abilities. Social media is a rather new phenomenon and due to its fast spread and its importance on major subjects and events, it has attracted the attention of the research (Lindahl et al. 2013).

2.9- Body Language

Body language is nonverbal contact that involves body movement. "Gesturing" can also be termed as body language which is absolutely non – verbal means of communication. People in this place of work can transmit a large deal of information with no even speaking; through nonverbal contact. How job seeker use and abuse his body determines how the job seeker feels about his self and how others perceive job seeker. Jobs are won and lost, reputations made and damaged, contact dissolved and cemented based on how the people involved, present them. People start making evaluations from the knowledge they first see job seeker and Add to those ingredients job seeker's body language, job seeker's manners, and job seeker's demeanor (Wiley et al. 2007).

2.10- Social Media in Self-Marketing

Manai & Aicha (2013) clarified that the social media (SM) has become relevant in almost all industries; it is in those various social media channels were persons directly go-to recommendations on everything ranging from food to sports to work positions and everything in among. Social media network (SMN) has been used in vocation hunting quite impact during the past years; Internet sites such as Yahoo, Job Central, and linkup between most of the others offer recent graduates and another searching for work to share a famous virtual platform where job seekers are offered the opportunity to sell themselves online, not to describe the self-marketing that takes place on places same LinkedIn and Facebook (Manai & Aicha, 2013). Discuss different tactics businesses must instrument when accessing SM and becoming active online. These tactics prove help for self-marketing as well. Identifying the necessity to sell one's self, adopting a marketer's mind frame, creating an active cover letter and curriculum vta (CV), organizing for an interview strategically and Identifying one's own downfalls and strengths, and evaluating ways on how to behave on social canals and online in general were all conversed in that they are the subjects most related to self-marketing on a truthful level; these activities must be adopted in order to successfully self-marketing (Manai & Aicha, 2013). The target is to provide students with a framework on progressing their self-marketing skills thus conversing the student's areas of importance in addition to the relevant idea was needful. Furthermore, self-marketing consists of direct methods of implementing

action running from simple CV writing to more complex situations as to how to communicate one's self in an interview situation (Manai & Aicha, 2013). Furthermore, SMN is a communication capability that is essential to effective engagement in globalized and multi-cultural cultures since it is key to schooling, employment, and daily life. While the notion of communication skills is of considerable importance in science and real-life contexts, because of the nature of communicating the term is usually difficult to describe (Vlad, 2020). The way we communicate with each other has transformed Social Media significantly. Letting the whole world participate in one's own life is possible now. The social media network offers the opportunity to create and maintain a personality quickly and more Cost- effectively. Artists from social media boss to all involved in creating a good personal identity on social media (Vlad, 2020). However, the incentives provided by social media to build a successful self-marketing identity are not restricted to companies or organizations alone. On the opposite, it is now more than ever feasible for ordinary people to equally take advantage of all the resources provided by social networking (Meiselwitz, g. 2019). They will be alerted when people want to follow an organization on Twitter, and their discussion can be checked in the dedicated feed. It helps define work openings, as well as create Twitter lists based on a personal profile. Organizations can be diligent about the phase because it is important to find the right employees at the right moment (Vlad, 2020).

2.11 - Creating Your Curriculum Vitae (CV) - Self Marketing:

2.11.1 - Divination Curriculum Vitae (CV)

The curriculum vitae are a Latin expression and translate to one's course of life, more commonly known as a CV in the modern world (Reed, 2018). Over and above the tactic your curriculum vitae are written and arranged lie important aim: Your curriculum vitae will encourage trust and motivate a recruiter to undertake the leap of faith by giving you a new individual interview is often a challenge to an interviewer, implying the CV mistakes and apparent exaggerations are an immense turnoff. On the other hand, there are plenty of ways in which you can present yourself as the most credible job applicant (Reed, 2018). According to Hanson (2018), Your CV can be the most essential career search document you need. It is a documented description of the knowledge, expertise, and qualifications relevant to your job. It provides a glimpse of the Certification. It sums up you, your abilities, and your abilities. It is a statement of who you are, what you have done, and what you hope to do next in your life. Your CV may be your first communication with a potential employer (Hanson, 2018).

CV stands for curriculum vitae, which can be translated simply as one's path of life. You won't have any aspect of your personal life in your curriculum vitae but you need to mention the obvious elements such as your name, experience of employment, contact information, schooling (Reed, 2018). Without these solid foundations, none of the other incredible things that you can do with your It's a little like papering a wall without filling in the gaps – you'll be happy with a fast finished outcome, but the flaws won't take long to breakthrough. What's more, you don't just want to write any old CV. You want to create a personal one for you. You will have strategies to get a position: applying for a job is not about dropping coins into a pool and praying that one of them will bring you luck. Employers like to feel unique and the Resume will make them believe their work is the only thing you would want to do in the country. More specifically, you ought to prove that you can do something different than anybody else who applies and an indiscriminate strategy won't allow you the chance to do so (Reed, 2018).

- The Curriculum Vitae

The goals of the resume are to be requested at the interview. Opposing to popular job seekers perform in the interview is what finally determines if a job seeker will be offered the location (Ghilani, 2010). Also, The goal of a resume is to show to the reader that job seekers are qualified or have the acting skills and experience for a position. The goal of preferring a resume is to lead to an interview. Because employers have many responsibilities and limited time, requirements need to know that a resume should say a lot in a very short manner (Ghilani, 2010). The resume should be a statement shorts his professionalism, abilities, and skills. The words and appearance offer the owner a first impression of the requirement (Solomon, et al., 2012). As explained by Solomon (2012), Relenting to the profession, the curriculum vitae (CV) may be appropriate. The CV is a detailed explanation of all professionals and pursuits academic, including professional positions and their related duties, publications, education endeavors, volunteer work, presentation is given and attended, the position held, organizational membership, the recognition that has been received, and honors. Although the functional resume or chronological is no more than two pages. The CV is most commonly used in research settings and academic. The explanation of a CV makes it applicable essentially for persons who have extensive credentials and experience (Solomon, 2012). Getting your CV right is a key component of your strategy to get the perfect job. Let's begin by looking at some of the fundamentals:

- The curriculum vitae should be honest.
- People are looking for gaps, so leave none without a workable clarification.
- We're motivated by appearance, however impartial we are meant to be, so make it look fine.
- Guarantee that your curriculum vitae are logical and not difficult to follow (Sara & Vincent, 2012).

Your CV has only one purpose and one aim: to win an interview with you. That means the person reading it will be persuaded that you have the potential to perform the specific work better than all of the other applicants. Many believe a curriculum vita can bring you jobs. But in truth, it's not. A curriculum vita has a specific function and that is to bring you into the interview place (Reed, 2018). This is best to have as while your passion and interests say your heart 's tale, your experience, and job background say your head 's story. In other terms, what you want to do in your free time may be more informative than what you choose to do in the job. There are a few elements that you should definitely leave out (your age, ethnicity, orientation, sex, gender, and religion (Reed, 2018).

2.12- Types of Resume (CV)

The most common CVs used today and surely powerfully recommended are the reverse chronological CV similar times referred to as the Functional CV and the Full CV (Brisk, 2011). Both kinds of the document have their place and it will be clarified when to use which one, together with the disadvantages and advantages that together of these bring in looking for employment. This CV might have a big name, but it is a straightforward document, and as the name proposes it captures a person's employment history beginning with the current activity and then working back in time. Relabeling on how long a person has been employed will affect how far back to go in time, as attention wants to be trained into going back many years and as the law of thumb, the last 10 to 12 years must be covered (Brisk, 2011).

2.12.1 - The Chronological Resume

The chronological resume lists professional skills and experiences in change chronological order. Chronological resumes are especially preferred by workforces because they are observed as face-based and can be simply reviewed (Doyle, 2008).

2.12.2 - The Functional Resume

The functional resume lists experience and skills by type slightly than chronologically. On a functional resume organization experience and knowledge from some positions would be gathered in one unit. Computer skills would be gathered in another. Some bosses may feel that the functional resume is greatly difficult to review, as it is lesser structured than a chronological resume and it is greatly difficult to associate skills and experience with a specific job (Doyle, 2008).

2.12.3 - Combination Resume

The referred to as Chrono- functional resume a combination resumes blends features of both chronological and functional resumes (Doyle, 2008).

2.13- Cover letter

Your presentation to the publisher is a cover note, informing Him or her a little about yourself and your job. Many editors in their lists Show their choice for cover letters. If an editor requires a cover letter, it is absolutely necessary to send one! If a cover letter is needed, it is easy to submit one too. Experts differ with the need and Appropriateness of cover letters but test yourself. A cover letter should be professional, but it should also encourage you to directly introduce your job. Keep brief about your letter, no more than one page. Give your letter to the contact individual who is right. If no communication name exists in the database, using Poetry Editor. Contain, if you submit a biographical notice, two or three lines regarding your history, ambitions, why you compose poetry, etc.

2.13.1 - Write a Connecting Cover Letter

First and foremost, the cover letter will include whatever detail is needed in the application notice containing the following:

Describe what you appreciate about the publication in a sentence or two, and why you want to apply your research- whether you have anything to tell that is genuine.

- Mentions the titles of the published poems. And this is an application at the same moment.
- To demonstrate your literary knowledge and skills, have a short biographical paragraph detailing main publications or educational highlights.

Be respectful and accommodating

- Do not provide explanations about why you chose these poems for submission, why you wrote them, what they mean to you or your family, or how you have revised them.
- Do not advise editors about then you expect to hear back from them.
- Do not send a follow- up the letter with a batch of poems that are edited versions of a previous submission.
- Send a follow-up letter to withdraw any poems you have submitted as soon as they have been accepted elsewhere (Brewer, 2018).

Almost no search can be behavior actively without a cover letter. Quite simply, the job seeker needs to send a letter or note that clears why job seekers are sending a resume. In spite of this, every practice will use most of the kind cover letters, depending on the circumstances: who job seeker's writing to and why job seeker's writing. Actually, a cover letter is exclusively created for every one of opportunity. Basically speaking, tried that job seeker's search is for the same positions in the same industry, a well – advanced cover letter should serve job seeker good for most contacts, with just minor modifications to customize it for every position. The cover letter should also be written specially to their intended listener (Kursmark et al. 2007).

2.14- Interview

An interview is a discussion between a prospective employer and a potential employee to decide whether or not they are acceptable to each other depending on the job's strengths, the qualifications needed to perform, and the attitudes needed to match in with the community (Sara & Vincent, 2012). The interview is one of the primary points in the work hunting process. Many other considerations that are not explicitly linked to the skill of the individual to do the job would be picked up in the interview. Obviously, at the interview, nobody will say precisely what questions they should be asking. If you don't answer a question correctly, do not be scared to return to the interview. As well as questions exploring particular fields, there are often numerous forms in which an interview may articulate their request. Most questions can generally be classified as either open or closed. A closed question is one that can very often be answered with just one word. In comparison, an open query is one that would compel a longer response. A good interviewer will usually ask open questions mainly because this is the question that will extract from you the most useful information. Many interviewers will start with a simple question and then probe the topic further by following up with another question. Never lie in an interview or say something that you cannot substantiate (Innes, 2012). On the other side, Dalton (2012) mentioned that an informational interview is a dialogue between an information seeker and an information maintainer (usually, but not necessarily, an individual at a target employer or one of the job seekers). The knowledge collector then continues the dialogue to collect pertinent information about the future of the information keeper and the progress through its new employer. Richard Bolles introduced this term in the career hunt smash back in 1976: Which color is your parachute? Yet that hasn't gone out of date yet. Actually, it is more important now than ever, as no hiring manager has time these days to genuinely consider every resume that is submitted to each online job posting (Dalton, 2012). That said, the act of performing an interview with information used to be enough in itself to advance you in the process. Informative interviews today need to be properly pursued, used, and leveraged to land an actual job interview (Dalton, 2012). In today's fiercely competitive job market, interviewing may seem like walking through a minefield (Yeager & Hough, 2019). Recent developments in organizational planning and development have contributed to drastic shifts in what managers search for in potential hires, so during the interview, you will be questioned regarding the kinds of issues (Yeager & Hough, 2019).

3- Methodology

3.1- Research Design

This study employed a qualitative method. The aim of using the qualitative approach is to gather information from the participants based on their ideas about undergraduate students, management, and existing structure. The qualitative research technique has been determined to develop awareness and attaining a possible understanding of the usage self-marketing for undergraduate students in Northern Iraq for finding the job. The semi-structured interview is being used in order to understand participants' perceptions of the effectiveness of self-marketing to engage a rational job.

3.2- Sampling and Data Collection

As a form of purposive sampling technique, the maximal variation sampling procedure was used. Each case, based on the selected sampling, would be identified in more detail by using this sampling strategy (Yıldırım and Şimşek 2006: 107). In this regard, twenty students of the University and Institute have been choosing for face to face interview in three city (Erbil, Sulamani, Duhok) from Northern Iraq. As samples three cities Erbil, sulamani, and Duhok cities are chosen and for each city, one College and one Institute is chosen and totally twenty

students in the final year will be interviewed as below: In Erbil city, Salahadin University, in the colleges four students and in the institutes four students will be interviewed. In Duhok city, Duhok University, in the colleges three students and in the institutes three students will be interviewed. In sulamani city, sulamani University, in the colleges three students and in the institutes three students will be interviewed (See table 4). Each semi-structured interview form embraces plenty of questions by which the best understanding of the problem and purpose of this research could be obtained and make an advantage for the research questions. The primary data for this research was gathered by semi-structured interviews which were handled with twenty students from Northern Iraq. The semi-structured interviews have been broadly used in the self-marketing context and delivered flexibility to change prior to and during the interview to become familiar with the flow of the discussion (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Then, in the light of the aim of this study, interview forms residing of twenty questions have been fixed. Each undergraduate student was communicated earlier in the interview and were informed regarding its content. May 1st, 2018 occurred the first interview and the last one on September June 1st, 2018, all interviews happened at the universities and institutes in three cities (Erbil, Duhok, and Sulaymaniyah) and they were recorded with the consent of the interviewees. Some of the interview questions which guided our study were as below:

- 1- Can you explain your experience and skills? Please, refer briefly?
- 2- Do you think the cirruclam vita (CV) is an essential ingredient to job seekers?
- 3- Do you think that the interview can play a prominent role to get work?
- 4- How do you estimate the importance of social media tools to find a job in your country?
- 5- Do you consider that the undergraduate students of northern Iraq have taken benefit from their profession to find a job?

Table 1: Research Participants

No.	Name Of Universities and Institutes	Students Participate	City	Studies' year
1	Salahaddin University	4	Erbil	Final year
2	Erbil Technology Institute	4	Erbil	Final year
3	Sulamani University	3	sulamani	Final year
4	Sleman Technology Institute	3	sulamani	Final year
5	Dhouk University	3	Dhouk	Final year
6	Duhok Technology Institute	3	Dhouk	Final year

3.3- Data Analysis

This thesis employed a methodology of content analysis to analyze and classify the results. According to the Hsieh & Shannon (2005: 1278), content analysis is a "research method for the subjective interpretation of the content of text through the systematic classification process of coding and identifying themes". Data were distributed in order to manage categories and discussed themes emerging from the study. During the review of this thesis, the participants (students) were marked with the abbreviations such as (the first student as Re#1, the second student as Re#2, Re#3 and so on).

Results

4.1- Participants' View on Social Media is a Strong Channel to Find a Job.

Development of social media has moved all business area, and Meiselwitz, g. (2019) explained that the social media network offers the opportunity to create and maintain a personality quickly and more cost-effectively. However, the incentives provided by social media to build a successful self-marketing identity are not restricted to companies or organizations alone. On

the opposite, it is now more than ever feasible for ordinary people to equally take advantage of all the resources provided by social networking (Meiselwitz, g. 2019).

This is true for undergraduate students to find the job by social media as it is also mentioned by Re#1, Re#5, Re#8, Re#9 and Re#20 as follows:

"The social media have the main role for finding work, especially these tolls like (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and so on), also the social media give information for these people who are jobless and they can receive information about finding work"

Additionally, the Re#8, Re#1, Re#15 confirmed a similar expression who said:

"We can obtain any information through the social media platform and if there is a job opportunity from any place, then you can realize it"

The same way, Re#15 and Re#16 had a similar understanding as they explained:

"We can use the social media application to make a relationship with our friends and relatives and they take benefit for finding a reasonable job"

As well as, the researcher asked Re#2, have you organized any goals to find a job? And Re#2 replied:

"If I can find work, then it will be easy to achieve my aim by collecting a lot of money and providing an interesting life"

Concerning Manai & Aicha (2013), social media network (SMN) has been used in vocation hunting quite impact during the past years; Internet sites such as Yahoo, Job Central, and linkup between most of the others offer recent graduates and another searching for work to share a famous virtual platform where job seekers are offered the opportunity to sell themselves online, not to describe the self-marketing that takes place on places same LinkedIn and Facebook. Discuss different tactics businesses must instrument when accessing SM and becoming active online. These tactics prove help for self-marketing as well, as Re#17, and 18 stated follows:

"Social media has many benefits because it is helpful to look for a job and you don't think the traditional way of finding a job. For this reason, social media is the finest and fast way to get a job"

The researcher asked an important question from all participants: How do you estimate the importance of social media tools to find a job in your country? And they all answered:

"Social media tools have an exceptional role in finding the job by these all sites that give a job opportunity for finding the job"

So that all the participants (100%) who have replied in this case, believe that social media plays the main role in finding a job.

4.2- Participants' View on CV is an Exceptional Way to Get a Reasonable Job

Reed (2018) explained that the curriculum vitae are a Latin expression and translate to one's course of life, more commonly known as a CV in the modern world. Over and above the tactic your curriculum vitae are written and arranged lie important aim: Your curriculum vitae will encourage trust and motivate a recruiter to undertake the leap of faith by giving you a new individual interview is often a challenge to an interviewer, implying the CV mistakes and apparent exaggerations are an immense turnoff. On the other hand, there are plenty of ways in which you can present yourself as the most credible job applicant (Reed, 2018), as well as, Re#1 stated this as follows:

"The CV actually has the main role for finding work, because CV always attracts owner work through these experience who you have that make the owner work designate you for the interview"

Also, we also asked this question from the participants: Do you consider that the undergraduate students of northern Iraq have taken benefit from their profession to find a job? And all of them replied:

"There is no doubt that the students study for four years in university and they obtain plenty of information at their department, as many students have taken advantage of finding the job that they are looking for"

The CV can be the most essential career search document you need. It is a documented description of the knowledge, expertise, and qualifications relevant to your job. It provides a glimpse of the Certification. It sums up you, your abilities, and your abilities. It is a statement of who you are, what you have done, and what you hope to do next in your life. Your CV may be your first communication with a potential employer (Hanson, 2018).

For this reason, some respondents such as Re#3, Re#7, Re#12, and Re#19 revealed the following same opinion:

"The CV has the finest role for finding a job, on condition that this CV will be owned rich information"

Almost no search can be behavior actively without a cover letter. Quite simply, the job seeker needs to send a letter or note that clears why job seekers are sending a resume. In spite of this, every practice will use most of the kind cover letters, depending on the circumstances: who job seeker's writing to and why job seeker's writing. Actually, a cover letter is exclusively created for every one of opportunity. Basically speaking, tried that job seeker's search is for the same positions in the same industry, a well – advanced cover letter should serve job seeker good for most contacts, with just minor modifications to customize it for every position. The cover letter should also be written specially to their intended listener (Kursmark et al. 2007). For this reason, the Re#1, Re#4, Re#9, and Re#15 gave the same explanation:

"For engaging a reasonable work, we must have a strong CV, experience, especially the cover letters have an effective role in the CV and it is another cause to attain the job"

On the other hand, the researcher asked one important question from participants: Have you tried to search for a job? They replied:

"Until now I have not had the ability to find the job, also I need more collecting information"

Also, Solomon (2012) elucidated that the explanation of a CV makes it applicable essentially for persons who have extensive credentials and experience (Solomon, 2012), as well as, getting your CV right is a key component of your strategy to get the perfect job. Let's begin by looking at some of the fundamentals: The curriculum vitae should be honest, people are looking for gaps, so leave none without a workable clarification, we are motivated by appearance, however impartial we are meant to be, so make it look fine, and guarantee that your curriculum vitae are logical and not difficult to follow (Sara & Vincent, 2012).

In this manner, Re#9, Re#10, Re#13, Re#16, and Re#18 had the same idea as mentioned:

"The CV has an influence on finding the job and it measures the person for revealing their skills, experience, and capability"

In addition, the Re#5 replied the following question that was asked in the research by the Interviewer: Do you think the curriculum vita (CV) is an essential ingredient to job seekers?

"Yes, a strong CV and more experience have a perfect role for supporting the CV. The interviewer can find all skills and experiences who the people have"

On the other side, some participants showed that being focused on a CV is not more a valuable way to attain the job, for example, the Re#14 referred to as follows:

"CV has no greater impact on finding a job"

According to Brisk (2011), the most common CVs used today and surely powerfully recommended are the reverse chronological CV similar times referred to as the Functional CV and the Full CV. Both kinds of the document have their place and it will be clarified when to use which one, together with the disadvantages and advantages that together of these bring in looking for employment. This CV might have a big name, but it is a straightforward document, and as the name proposes it captures a person's employment history beginning with the current activity and then working back in time. Relabeling on how long a person has been employed will affect how far back to go in time, as attention wants to be trained into going back many years and as the law of thumb, the last 10 to 12 years must be covered (Brisk, 2011). Therefore, other participants expressed a similar view:

"We can say that CV big name and fifty percent of finding work that indicates having a strong and influential CV, therefore anyone wants to obtain the job, they must try to make a powerful CV for finding the job"

4.3- Participants' View on the Value of Certifications, Skills, and Experience in Self-Marketing.

Reed (2018) explained, employability means hiring and staying hired with skills and skills and using them. Even if you can diagnose and repair the most complex networking problems, if the client thinks you are unfriendly, or if coworkers feel resentful that you're coming in late each day, you might lose your job, and also Re#1, and Re#4 discussed as below:

"The skill is more important to find the job, also it is one of the main that you do not lose your job, as well as if you have the skills, the workers will be owned many perfect specifications, such as making trusts, and friendly which is helping you to continue on work"

Also, the most significant question of this thesis that some participants could give the exact answer to the interviewer is: What are your strengths and weaknesses point to find a job? Except the Re#20, another participant said:

"The strength point is sincere: Trusting, knows more than languages and computers, calm and indulgent person, and skills and experiences, but the weaknesses point is: Merciful, to make a rash decision, worried, scared, tiredness emotional personality, and shy"

Furthermore, Skills are the technical competences a person possesses. Skills are a fairly simple concept; soft abilities are much more difficult to pin down applying to as they do to a range of skills. Essential Skills: Each and every student must possess the essential skills in order to strive and to survive in the competitive world. The learners in the traditional setting predominantly constitute student preparing for a career. The learning system focuses on class-room based students and overarches the design and operation of the teaching (Bhatnagar & Bhatnagar, 2012), In this manner, the Re#5, Re#7, Re#8, Re#11, and Re#12 have the same clarifications:

"We know two foreign languages without the mother tongue. Also, we have worked in my field during the summer holiday. Additionally, we have a reasonable experience form some computer"

programs. So that if you know some international languages, so you own a skills and capability, then it will be easy to find the job"

The researcher asked many important questions from participants whom this thesis such as: If you could not find a job interested what would you do? What motivates you to get work? Would you prefer the training program before an employee? And while in university, what sort of duties has to do to develop your job search? Hence, all respondents except Re#20, presented the logic answers:

"We always try to find reasonable work, also we have experience from the accounting department, and with several contemporary sciences, such as some program computers and so on, also until obtaining an interesting life and collect money and I will be on of the richest person around the world. Furthermore, you must-have information, before you will find work or take a course until you will be strong and it provides power for your CV, especially when you have an interview with the owner's work and wait for many questions if they orientate you and then you can answer them successfully. Lastly, these courses that we have studied from the university will be expanding your skills and ability, and it is valuable for finding the work"

On the contrary, the Re#20 mentioned a different opinion:

"The Certification, skills, and experience do not have a large role to find the job"

Moreover, other respondents (Re#2, Re#3, Re#6, Re#9, Re#10, Re#13, Re#14, Re#15, Re#16, Re#17, Re#18 and Re#19) had the similar opinion:

"The skills, certification, experience, and language have an exceptional role in self- marketing, particularly to find the job"

4.4- Participants' View on the Interview is a Powerful Instrument For Job Seekers

Sara & Vincent (2012) said, An interview is a discussion between a prospective employer and a potential employee to decide whether or not they are acceptable to each other depending on the job's strengths, the qualifications needed to perform, and the attitudes needed to match in with the community, as well as Re#5, Re#7, and Re#19 referred to this as below:

"The interview has a special role in finding a job because it shows the ability of a person during the interview"

Concerning Yeager & Hough, (2019), in today's fiercely competitive job market, interviewing may seem like walking through a minefield. Recent developments in organizational planning and development have contributed to drastic shifts in what managers search for in potential hires, so during the interview, you will be questioned regarding the kinds of issues (Yeager & Hough, 2019), so the Re#10 clarified:

"Without an interview, you can not find the right person for the right place, therefore, the interview is essential for finding the job"

A good interviewer usually asks open questions mainly because this is the question that will extract from you the most useful information. Many interviewers will start with a simple question and then probe the topic further by following up with another question. Never lie in an interview or say something that you cannot substantiate (Innes, 2012), in the same way, the researcher asked the simple or an open question from participants: What are your hobbies? And the Re#1, Re#4 replied:

"When I can finish the study, I would like to find a reasonable work" "I want to develop my profession and have an interesting life" Additionally, the participants had the same view: "We can find a good job in the near term"

Dalton (2012) mentioned that an information interview is a dialogue between an information seeker and an information maintainer (usually, but not necessarily, an individual at a target employer of one of the job seekers). The knowledge collector then continues the dialogue to collect pertinent information about the future of the information keeper and the progress through its new employer., additionally the Re#9, and Re#12 mentioned:

"After trying to find a job, then you get the interview stage with the owner's work to close your case that Do they accept you or not? So, the interview is one of the important stages to find the job, therefore we must pay attention to the interview"

Accordingly, the researcher asked a vital question from respondents:

Do you think that the interview can play a prominent role to get work?

Except for the Re#18, all other respondents expressed the same explanation:

"Yes, the interview has an important role in finding the job and they must prepare for the interview in the most reliable way"

Furthermore, every other respondents such as Re#1, Re#2 Re#3, Re#4, Re#6, Re#8, Re#11, Re#13, Re#14, Re#15, Re#16, Re#17, and Re#20 expressed the similar explanation:

"We consider the interview is extremely important because the owner's work can realize the abilities and skills person during the interview"

Contrarily, one of the respondents' researches expressed a different opinion, for instance, Re#18 mentioned as follows:

"The interview does not play a vital role in finding a job"

Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

The purpose of this study was to understanding undergraduate students about self-marketing to find a reasonable job when the students graduate must increase their information regarding many important points in self-marketing such as (CV, Interview, Social media, and skills and experience). After completion of the study, substantial data have been collected in the forms of literature reviews, and undergraduate students about the understanding of self-marketing to find the job in Northern Iraq. Based on the results of this study the conclusion that can be drawn could contribute to the overall discussion of the role of self-marketing. Because of this research, it is realized that there are some problems in finding a job in Northern Iraq, therefore this research could find the solution for the main problem, which is the lack of understanding of the undergraduate students in Northern Iraq about the effective usage of the self-marketing to find the job. Today, Self-marketing is necessary so that people will see you as deserving of the opportunities that you seek and so that they will be more inclined to share time and expertise with you. If you're not marketing yourself, you are going to fall behind someone else. You need to embrace and actively engage with the concept of self-marketing or else you'll always be on the fringe You need credentials and visibility (Silber, 2010). There is a vigorous theme that link with using the social media is a robust channel to find a job. Results showed that the social media is the best factor to practice self- marketing and this tool assists you to have the ability to find a job successfully. As explained by Meiselwitz, g. (2019), the social media network offers the opportunity to create and maintain a personality quickly and more cost-effectively. However, the incentives provided by social media to build a successful self-marketing identity are not restricted to companies or organizations alone. On the opposite, it is now more than ever feasible for ordinary people to equally take advantage of all the resources provided by social networking

(Meiselwitz, g. 2019). Therefore, the undergraduate students of Northern Iraq must pay attention to social media platforms to find the job.

Another theme relates to the power of interviews for job seekers. Results presented that the interview has run a significant function in self-marketing, especially it is important to undergraduate students (universities and institutes) to attain the job. In today's fiercely competitive job market, interviewing may seem like walking through a minefield. Recent developments in organizational planning and development have contributed to drastic shifts in what managers search for in potential hires, so during the interview, you will be questioned regarding the kinds of issues (Yeager & Hough, 2019). For this reason, the undergraduate students (universities and institutes) in Northern Iraq must know the truth that interviews one of the important forms of self-marketing for progressing the job seekers during the searching job. One of the arguments defends the CV is an exceptional way to get a reasonable job. Results showed that CV has occupied a large part in self-marketing, as well as it makes the best relationship between the employers and job seekers to find the job. As clarified by Hanson, (2018), the CV can be the most essential career search document you need. It is a documented description of the knowledge, expertise, and qualifications relevant to your job. It provides a glimpse of the Certification. It sums up you, your abilities, and your abilities. It is a statement of who you are, what you have done, and what you hope to do next in your life. Your CV may be your first communication with a potential employer (Hanson, 2018). So that, the undergraduate students in Northern Iraq must realize the concepts of CV fully, because the CV is Vital to find the job. The additional subject is regarding the value of certifications, skills, and experience in self-marketing. Results showed that by increasing certifications, skills, and experience are causing riching the CV to accept yours by the employers. According to Bhatnagar & Bhatnagar, (2012), skills are the technical competences a person possesses. Skills are a fairly simple concept; soft abilities are much more difficult to pin down applying to as they do to a range of skills. Essential Skills: Each and every student must possess the essential skills in order to strive and to survive in the competitive world. The learners in the traditional setting predominantly constitute student preparing for a career. The learning system focuses on class-room based students and overarches the design and operation of the teaching (Bhatnagar & Bhatnagar, 2012). Therefore, if the undergraduate students (universities and institutes) in Northern Iraq increase their certifications, skills, ability, and experience, then they can get reasonable work. In conclusion, this study found that the effectiveness and efficiency of self-marketing, especially (CV, interview, SM, and skills, experience, and certification student) are the foremost way to undergraduate students (universities and institutes) in Northern Iraq to thrive the compete of finding a job. This study is limited to undergraduate students' participation. For future research, employers can do marketing for their profession.

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